

INVESTIGATION OF THE FORMATION OF MICROSTRUCTURE AND STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF SLAG-ALKALINE ARBOLITE

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Abstract

The creation of the slag-alkaline arbolite's structure is examined in this study, which is based on measurements of the deformation of the mortar component, contact zone, and filler. Composites made of slag and alkaline arbolite are among the lightest building materials available, with excellent sound insulation and low thermal conductivity. Standard measuring equipment and procedures for analyzing the chemical and physico-mechanical properties of slag-alkaline arbolite composites were employed during the experimental tests. All of the test samples were light concrete prisms with a cross section of 150×150 mm and a length of 600 mm. For comparison, one portion of the samples was constructed of slag-alkaline Portland cement, and the other portion was made of slag-alkaline binder with crushed cotton stem fibers as an organic component. The durability and deformability of arbolite were tested under Republic of Kazakhstan weather conditions and in standard hardening chambers. The arbolite underwent a compression stress that ranged from (0.3 to 0.75) R_{bn} of prismatic strength. It was discovered that the organic cellulose filler added to the slag-alkaline binder based on crushed cotton stalk fiber, which makes up to 70 % of the volume, has a major impact on the way structures are formed. The system becomes rigid, the elasticity changes, and the acoustic properties in this case will fix both physical and physico-chemical processes when a porous organic filler is added. The acquired results can be applied to the creation of efficient wall materials for civil buildings, including seismic zones.

Keywords: microstructure, strength, stress, deformation, slag-alkali arbolite, structure formation, shrinkage, concrete hardening, prism samples.

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1. Introduction

The need for building materials and structures is growing daily as a result of the rapidly developing construction sector in Kazakhstan's regions, so it is important to produce structural and thermal insulation materials using secondary resources. Slag-alkaline arbolite concrete composites, which combine lightness, environmental friendliness, high thermal insulation qualities, and can contain plant and agricultural waste, which are abundant in the regions of Republic of

Kazakhstan, hold a special place in the production of building materials in the regions of Republic of Kazakhstan with a sharply continental climate. Yet, the task of further increasing its construction and operational, technological, strength, and deformation indicators presents itself due to the rising requirements for the quality of arbolite concrete composites.

We have discovered that by deliberately altering the qualities and structure of arbolite concrete composites with various additives of industrial and plant waste, it is feasible to enhance their properties. According to the analysis of numerous data the slag-alkaline components of the mortar part significantly affect the strength and deformation characteristics of conventional arbolite based on wood crushing, where organic cellulose aggregate based on crushed fiber cotton stems is frequently the least durable component. The mechanism of slag-alkaline arbolite's deformation and destruction under sustained load at various compressive stresses, as well as the development of its microstructure and strength characteristics, are hence relevant investigations.

Slag-alkaline binders' increased activity permits the use of a variety of fillers, including organic waste with a plant origin. In today's world, it is crucial for each region to have access to local resources in order to obtain binders and materials based on them that adhere to strict technical standards and support environmental preservation. Since wood is scarce in Republic of Kazakhstan and Central Asia, arbolite can be produced using agricultural waste and different plants, such as crushed cotton stalks, as an organic filler. Cotton stems resemble wood in structure and chemical content because of their more uniformly folded shape.

It is known of the works [1] devoted to the creation and investigation of arbolite-concrete materials and constructions. The findings made [2] it possible to identify the peculiarities of these materials' attributes and structure development, to sketch out potential improvements, and to pinpoint potential application areas. Joint work between organic aggregate and slag-alkali binder is demonstrated in works. As a result [3], it was discovered that the slag-alkali binder, which during mixing envelops the particle surfaces and seeps into their irregularities [4], fissures, and pores, provides the link between the particles of organic aggregate in the aqueous medium. After a specific amount of time, adhesion develops between the aggregate grains and the slag-alkali binder stone as a result of the slag-alkali binder's subsequent hardening [5]. Arbolite's qualities and properties are mostly determined by the adhesion value. It has been demonstrated in works [6] that structural arbolite with a strength of 1.5–6.0 MPa and a density of 600–950 kg/m³ can be produced using cellulose organic aggregates. Arbolite's composition contains light, porous organic aggregate particles that increase the material's performance by reducing its density, thermal conductivity, and brittleness and by allowing it to be sawed and processed with a variety of instruments [7]. Arbolite has strength, biostability, fire resistance, frost resistance, and other characteristics that make it more durable thanks to its mineral binder [8]. Compositions of slag-alkali arbolite made of phosphorus slag, liquid glass, and crushed cotton stalks are known [9]. The final product has a compressive strength ranging from 1.7 to 4.5 MPa [10]. It is also advised in these works to heat treat the items using isothermal curing at 353 °K. In works [11], it is demonstrated that the use of chemically active aluminum, chlorine, alkaline metal, and salts of sulfuric acid compounds enables the formation of cementitious formations with increased condensation of silicon-oxygen anions, thereby increasing the strength of silicate stone used in autoclave materials. In this instance, the addition of man-made raw materials to the concrete mixture specifically, slag and Portland slag cement plays a beneficial role by promoting the formation of new crystals with a predominance of «abnormal» varieties of tobermorite in their makeup [12]. This enhances the material's strength properties and lessens shrinkage deformations [13]. The importance of aggregate in boosting concrete's strength was demonstrated in [14]. The aggregate has a particularly strong impact on the characteristics of lightweight concrete, because the aggregate's strength is typically lower than the concrete's own strength. Concrete on a specific aggregate at a specific cement rate is thought to have a limit, or «critical» strength, which only rises as the aggregate's ultimate strength and deformability do [15]. However according to [16], concrete fails when one of its constituent parts hits the limit of compressibility. The maximum strength of lightweight concrete is reached if this aggregate is porous, meaning that further increases in the strength and compressibility of the mortar component do not result in increases in the strength and deformability of concrete. According

to work [17], the compressibility of lightweight concrete has increased somewhat. The limited deformability of the mortar that is only present in the space between the aggregate grains, however, accounts for the relatively little growth that has been seen. The strength growth limit of the mortar component determines the «final strength of lightweight concrete on a given porous aggregate», according to the author of [18]. As all other factors remain constant, an increase in the mortar part's strength from 4.4 to 47.3 MPa results in a virtually linear rise in the strength of lightweight concrete, with no tendency for attenuation in the high value region. The dispersibility of a binder's composition determines its eventual strength. According to [19], when the characteristics of porous aggregate and cement stone converge, the best strength and deformability features of lightweight concretes can be obtained. The authors [20, 21] note that in this situation, the deformative characteristics of both concrete components converge, causing a slight stress concentration and complete manifestation of the strength characteristics of cellulose organic aggregate in such a composition under external force action. In contrast to the traditional arbolite based on wood crushing, where the organic cellulose aggregate is frequently the least strong component, analysis of a number of data [22] reveals that the slag-alkali components of the mortar part have a significant influence on its strength and deformability characteristics. Building and structural bearing capacities are significantly impacted by the investigation of lightweight concrete creep, which includes arbolite [23]. For the purpose of making informed decisions about the number of storeys to use when building load-bearing and enclosing wall constructions, the study of creep processes in arbolite concretes is crucial. It was expected that similar regularities would also apply to slag-alkali arbolite because it is known [24] that the creep of slag-alkali keramsite concrete is primarily dictated by the creep of the gel contained in the cement stone. Slag-alkali arbolite's prism strength coefficient was calculated in line with the suggestions made in the study literature [25]. Arbolite that contains sulfur has a coefficient of prism strength that is, on average, 25 % higher than that of traditional lightweight concrete. This difference can be attributed to the peculiarities of its deformative properties, which are distinguished by higher ultimate tensile strength [26].

The data analysis reveals that using high-strength binding agents to achieve high-performance arbolitic concrete can maximize the strength of the mortar component of arbolite while fully realizing the properties of cellulose organic aggregate, creating the ideal conditions for the formation of an arbolitic concrete structure with high strength and low density.

The study's goal is to create high-strength arbolite concrete composites based on alkali-alkali binders, the production of their microstructure, and structure formation processes employing crushed cotton stem fiber for use as a wall material for residential construction.

The following assignments were made to accomplish the objective:

1. Research into how the structure of slag-alkaline arbolite, which is based on crushed cotton stalks, is formed.
2. During the hardening process and in accordance with the findings of measurements of the deformation of the mortar component, the contact zone, and the filler.

Arbolite becomes more deformable when organic cellulose aggregates like shredded cane or cotton stalks are used, necessitating further experimental and experimental labor to boost its stiffness and hardness. The theory of arbolite concrete's creep and deformability is now far from being finished, and a number of intricate problems need theoretical and experimental investigation.

2. Materials and methods

An experimental investigation was carried out using electric steelmaking slag from the Aktobe Metallurgical Combine and electrothermophosphoric slag from the Shymkent Production Association. Slags were employed as powders that had been ground to a particular surface in accordance with PSK-2 (320–330 m²/kg) and in accordance with GOST 13015.0-83, GOST 3476-74, GOST 10180-90, GOST 7076-99, and OST 67-11-84.

Alkaline components included sodium silicate (GOST 13078-81) and a sodium sulfate mixture made from caprolactam production waste (GOST 10689-75 and TU 113-03-23-19-83).

Fly ash from the Aktobe CHP was utilized as an active mineral additive and complied with GOST 25592-91 and GOST 10181-2000.

The properties of the fly ash produced by the Aktobe CHP include specific surface area of 2550 cm²/g, absorption activity of 32 mg/g, actual density of 2000 kg/m³, and bulk density of 955 kg/m³. **Table 1** provides information on the chemical make-up of fly ash.

In order to control the processes of structure formation of the binder, alkaline components were used in the form of aqueous solutions. The composition of the alkaline components by volume is given in **Table 2**.

Table 1
Chemical composition of fly ash

Losses during calcination, mass %	Content of oxides, mass %						
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃ +TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	NaO ₂	SO ₂
7.33	48.3	23.92	5.94	9	1.9	0.18	0.52

Table 2
Composition of alkaline components by volume

No.	Name of alkaline components	The content of the solution of the alkaline component, l	Density of alkaline components, kg/m ³
1	Sodium silicate, soluble	0.5	1300
2	Sodium sulfate mixture	0.5	1200
3	Sodium silicate, soluble	0.75	1200
4	Sodium sulfate mixture	0.25	1300

Comparative studies also included the use of synthetic clinker materials and Portland cement grades 400 and 500 (GOST 10178-85). **Tables 3, 4** provide information on the physico-mechanical characteristics and chemical-mineralogical makeup of the aforementioned clinker minerals used in Portland cement.

Table 3
Physical and mechanical properties of Portland cement

Normal dough density	The beginning of setting	End of setting	Compressive strength, MPa	Bending strength, MPa	Blurring of the cone, mm
25.2 %	2 h–39 min	4 h–29 min	42.7	5.7	110

Table 4
Chemical composition of Portland cement, mass %

CaO	SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	MgO	SO ₃	R ₂ O	PP	Σ
61.48	23.38	6.09	6.38	1.09	0.60	0.38	0.52	99.92

In compliance with GOST 310.1-76, 310.2-76, 310.3-76, 310.4-76, 25820-2000, and 10060.3-95, Portland cement was tested. GOST 25820-2000 and GOST 7473-94 stipulate that Portland cement must include at least 40 % silica and no more than 3 % sulfuric acid anhydride, as well as no more than 10 % loss during calcination. The composition of the solution of the alkaline component was chosen in order to analyze the processes of interaction and creation of the phase composition of fly ash-based slag-alkaline binder compositions. By encapsulating the ground slags with solutions of alkaline components, a slag-alkaline binder was made. Along with the water for mixing, the alkaline component was added in the form of a solution that had a density of 1100–1300 kg/m³. The strength of the binder was assessed using GOST 3476-74 and GOST 7473-94 standards. According to GOST 25820-2000, the typical density and setting time were determined. The samples were compressed on the VS-1 vibrating platform for three minutes. Samples that had

undergone steaming and in-vivo hardening were used in the investigation. Cotton stem fibers that have been crushed were employed as an organic filler to conduct experiments. Crushed cotton stem fibers' physical-chemical characteristics, chemical composition, and fractional composition were determined experimentally in accordance with GOST 19222-84 and GOST 25820-2000 requirements, as well as on the basis of reference and literature data, and they are shown in **Tables 5, 6**:

Table 5
Chemical composition of crushed fibers of cotton stems

Crushed cotton fibers	Content of components, %			
	Cellulose	Lignin	Pentazone	Polysaccharides
	39.1	19.2	17.7	24

Table 6
Fractional composition of crushed fibers of cotton stems

Types of residues	Residue, % by weight, on sieves with cell size, mm					
	40	20	10	5	2.5	1.25
Private Complete	Non-dispersed fibers of cotton stems					
	–	16	2.4	46.6	19	13
Private Complete	Scattered fibers of cotton stems					
	–	–	7.6	19.0	59.0	10.0
	–	–	7.6	26.6	85.5	95.6

The best composition for the alkaline component solution was initially chosen by experimental means. The samples underwent heat treatment as well as a natural hardening process. Standard techniques in accordance with GOST 19222-84 were used to investigate the characteristics of organic aggregates.

The following steps were taken to prepare the arbolite mixture: first, the slag was dry mixed with cellulose organic aggregate in the form of crushed cotton stalks; next, an already prepared solution of the alkaline component was added; and finally, the mixture was mixed until a homogeneous mass was achieved.

To investigate the impact of these variables on the physico-mechanical properties of arbolite, a wide range of solution-slag (R/W) ratio and density of alkaline component solutions were used. The completed arbolite mixture was poured into a 10×10×10 cm, clean, lubricated mold, bayoneted, compacted, and set in line with GOST 19222-84 specifications.

Slag-alkaline arbolite's composition, characteristics, and technology were optimized through mathematical experiment planning and experimental testing. Arbolite's physical and mechanical properties were assessed using GOST 19222-84, 25820-2000, 7076-99, 7473-94, 10060.0-95, and 3476-97 as guides. The research used natural, heat treatment, and steaming as different methods of sample hardening.

In order to get adequate complete and trustworthy information on the activities taking place during contact of the binder with the filler, a series of independent methodologies were applied to analyze the contact zone between the organic aggregate and the slag-alkaline binder.

A combination of X-ray, thermogrammic, and derivatothermal methods of investigation were used to examine the phase composition of the arbolite contact zone. On a DRON-2.0 diffractometer, X-ray phase analysis was performed. With rotation speeds of 1 and 2 degrees per minute for the sample and counters, X-ray pictures of SI radiation were captured over the range of angles $2\theta = 2-60^\circ$. Radiographs were decoded by matching the acquired data to descriptions of natural and synthetic minerals found in the literature.

Optical microscopy was used to analyze the structure of arbolite on various porous aggregates. On the MBS-4 microscope, optical-microscopic examinations of the sections were performed in

reflected light. Using an EM-7 electron microscope, the microstructures of the contact zones were examined in greater detail. Photographs were taken as the arbolite structure was examined.

The UK-10PM device was used to measure the propagation velocity of longitudinal waves associated with changes in the elastic characteristics of the material as well as the values of the period of the predominant wave of the pulse oscillation frequency spectrum characterizing the change in its structure in order to study the kinetics of the process of structure formation of slag-alkaline arbolite at a temperature of 10–80 °C.

In chambers that simulate normal hardening circumstances and the environment of Kazakhstan, studies of the strength and deformability of arbolite were conducted. When the material had hardened for 28 days in a natural environment, shrinkage deformations were measured. Using prism samples with a dimension of 150x150x600 mm, the creep of slag-alkaline arbolite was investigated under sustained loading. The investigation was conducted 28 days following thermal, heat, and humidity treatments as well as in vivo hardening. From the prismatic strength, the arbolite's compression stress ranges from (0.3 to) $0.75 R_{bn}$.

The temperature changed during the test period:

- in climatic conditions: from –25 to 42 °C with relative humidity in the range of 70 to 80 %;
- in normal hardening chambers: from 16 to 22 °C at a relative humidity of 90 to 96 %.

The study of the special properties of arbolite (thermal conductivity, fire resistance, biostability) was carried out with a wide variation of the studied factors.

The Department of Physics at Aktobe Regional State University collaborated with the Department of «Design and Construction» of the institution «Baishev University» to perform studies on the thermal conductivity of arbolite in dry and natural conditions as well as after heat treatment. For a very long time, observations of the state of slag-alkaline arbolite samples were made under the direct effect of atmospheric conditions. **Table 7** displays the investigated slag-alkaline arbolite compositions based on cotton stem fibers that have been crushed.

Table 7

Compositions of the studied slag-alkaline samples of arbolite based on crushed fibers of cotton stems

No.	Material consumption per 1 m ³ arbolite					Density, kg/m ³
	Organic filler	Aluminosilicate component		Alkaline component, l		
	Crushed fibers of cotton stems, kg	Electrothermophosphoric slag, kg	Fly ash consumption, kg	Sodium sulfate mixture	Liquid glass	
1	140	200	250	125	125	450
2	145	220	200	125	125	420
3	150	240	250	250	–	550
4	160	260	250	125	125	500
5	170	280	200	125	125	420
6	180	300	250	250	–	600

Using low-frequency monochromatic oscillations at the installation and pulsed ultrasonic method at later stages of hardening, the kinetics of the formation of the arbolite structure from the moment of mixing with alkaline solutions of the mixture and during their subsequent prolonged hardening were measured.

The installation also enables the measurement of the resonant frequency f_p of the volume of material situated between the longitudinal walls of the mold on the base $l = 10$ cm while utilizing monochromatic oscillations. To do this, alter the generator's frequency and set its resonant value, f_p , at which the oscillations on the screen have their greatest amplitude. In this instance, the selective amplifier's gain frequency range is tuned in accordance with the region in which resonance is detected. Fix the front of the pulse signal's duration as well as the values for vt of the velocity of the longitudinal waves of the ultrasonic frequency using an ultrasonic instrument.

The results of studies on the identification of the main factors affecting the properties of slag-alkaline arbolites allow to conclude that in order to obtain them, a set of the most favorable

factors is necessary, which determine the achievement of the selected optimality criterion in each case. The structure of the studied materials is also being formed. The features of the processes of structure formation largely determine the main characteristics of the developed slag-alkaline arbolites, which makes it possible to predict and regulate their properties.

Using electrothermophosphoric slags in normal conditions on compositions of grades 15, 25, and 35 with alkaline components based on sodium sulfite, sodium sulfate, sodium silicate, and a sodium sulfate mixture, the structure formation of hardening arbolite concrete was explored (Table 8).

Table 8
Compositions and properties of slag-alkaline arbolite

No.	Arbolite brand	Type of slag	The alkaline component		Fly ash-based additives, %	Compressive strength, MPa
			Type	Density, kg/m ³		
1	25	electrothermophosphoric slag	Na ₂ SO ₃	1200	–	3.5
2	35	electrothermophosphoric slag	SSM	1300	3	4.3
3	25	electrothermophosphoric slag	Na ₂ O ₂ SiO ₃	1300	–	3.45
4	15	electrothermophosphoric slag	CCC	1100	5	1.8
5	15	electrothermophosphoric slag	Na ₂ SO ₄	1100	3	1.7

Notes: ETP slag-electrothermophosphoric slag; SSM – sodium sulfate mixture

To compare the variations, blast furnace slags based on the alkaline components Na₂SO₃, Na₂S₂O₃, and Na₂SO₄ were also used. Alkaline component density ranged from 1100 to 1300 kg/m³ concurrently. Crushed cotton stem fiber and a slag-alkaline solution component were combined to form slag-alkaline arbolite, with the strength of the solution component being changeable (Tables 9, 10).

Table 9
Test results of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete samples without fiber of cotton stems

Slag – alkaline binder			Compressive strength of the mortar part, R_{cube} , MPa	Without fiber of cotton stems		
Slag	The alkaline component			Prismatic strength, R_{pr} , MPa	Modulus of elasticity of the solution part of the arbolite	Poisson's ratio μ_p
	Type	The density of the alkaline solution				
Electrothermophosphoric slag	SSM	1100	55	4.02	2.27	0.19
Blast furnace slag	Na ₂ O ₂ SiO ₂	1300	90	3.44	3.12	0.18
Blast furnace slag	Na ₂ CO ₃	1150	30	2.11	1.75	0.23
Electrothermophosphoric slag	Na ₂ O ₂ SiO ₂	1200	60	4.44	2.31	0.18
Portland Cement	Water	–	30	1.98	1.68	0.19

Table 10
Results of tests of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete samples with fibers of cotton stems

Slag – alkaline binder			Compressive strength of the mortar part, R_{cube} , MPa	Without fiber of cotton stems		
Slag	The alkaline component			Prismatic strength, R_{pr} , MPa	Modulus of elasticity of the solution part of the arbolite	Poisson's coefficient of ciant μ_{ar} (arbolite-wood concrete) wood concrete
	Type	The density of the alkaline solution				
Electrothermophosphoric slag	IIB	1100	55	3.00	1.65	0.26
Blast furnace slag	Na ₂ O ₂ SiO ₂	1300	90	4.07	2.37	0.23
Blast furnace slag	Na ₂ CO ₃	1150	30	1.51	1.20	0.28
Electrothermophosphoric slag	Na ₂ O ₂ SiO ₂	1200	60	3.00	2.0	0.22
Portland Cement	Water	–	30	1.15	1.21	0.31

Four sample series were created for testing, and a fifth series was created on Portland cement for comparison. Each series contained six samples of prisms of 15×15×60 cm, three of which (model I) only had the mortar portion, and the other three (model II) had a center filled with crushed cotton stalk fibers that ranged in size from 20 to 40 mm. Prior to testing, all samples underwent heat and moisture treatment before being stored in a natural laboratory environment. Using strain gauges with a base of 10 to 50 mm and fast-hardening adhesive «Cyacrin EO», the longitudinal and transverse deformations experienced during the loading of samples were recorded (**Fig. 1**). Cotton stalks with sanded ends were tested for compression of granules of individual fiber grains in order to compare the strength and elastic properties of the fiber utilized. The cotton stalks had a bulk density of 600 kg/m³ and a compressive strength in a standard cylinder of 2.0 MPa. The findings of testing 10 cotton stem single fibers with dimensions of 20–40 mm and a height-to-diameter ratio of 1–2 revealed that the cotton stem fiber's average strength is 2.0 MPa, its elastic modulus is 3400 MPa, and its Poisson's ratio is 0.27 (**Fig. 1**).

Based on these findings, graphical dependences are created for samples that just contain the mortar component, samples that also contain cotton stem fiber, and samples that have crushed cotton stem fiber embedded in slag-alkaline arbolite concrete.

Fig. 1. Scheme of installation of deep strain gauges as part of slag-alkaline arbolite samples:
1 – strain gauge on crushed fibers of cotton stems; 2 – strain gauge in slag-alkaline solution

The strain resistors installed on the fibers of cotton stems and on the surface of the samples worked mostly stably up to the load (0.9–1) R_{np} of concrete.

3. Results and discussion

It is discovered that the organic cellulose filler added to the slag-alkaline binder based on crushed cotton stalk fiber, which makes up to 70 % of the volume, has a major impact on the way structures are formed. The system becomes rigid, the elasticity changes, and the acoustic properties in this case will fix both physical and physico-chemical processes when a porous organic filler is added. According to studies, the periods of structure formation at the beginning of hardening differ in length when crushed cotton stalks are added to a slag-alkaline solution as opposed to periods of structure creation in a slag-alkaline binder without fillers. Hence, the first stage of the coagulation structure of pure slag-alkaline dispersion takes 15 minutes longer to form than the slag-alkaline arbolite concrete structure, which takes 25 minutes. It can be inferred that the processes taking place during the hardening between a slag-alkaline binder and an organic filler have the active role of generating a dense, long-lasting contact layer between them. This is further supported by the strength of the arbolite slag-alkaline binding stone, which rises from 7.8 MPa per day at 3 and 7 days of age to 19 and 28 MPa, respectively. The increase in strength of the forming stone of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete is thus demonstrated to be intimately related to the processes of structure formation. By altering their compositions, slag-alkaline arbolite concrete can have its structure formed under control.

It is established that the dependence of the strength of slag-alkaline concrete on the initial strength of the solution consists of two sections, which, according to characterize the work of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete in the first and second phases (**Fig. 2**). The first section, in which an increase in the strength of the mortar part entails a proportional increase in strength, corresponds to a more intense to increase the strength of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete (from 2.51 to 4.0 MPa) with a change in the initial strength of its mortar part (from 20 to 45 MPa). At the same time, the corresponding calculated strength of the crushed fiber of cotton stems and the mortar part in arbolite concrete increases: The strength of arbolite concrete R_{arb} increases by 100 % (from 1.7 to 3.94 MPa), and the strength of the slag-alkaline solution R_p – by 98 % (from 15.7 to 30.9 MPa). The second section is characterized by a slow increase in the strength of arbolite concrete (from 3.0 to 4.17 MPa) with a significant increase in the initial strength of its solution (from 55.0 to 90.0 MPa). At the same time, the average design strength of the mortar part increases by 45 % (from 30.3 to 43.6 MPa), and the average stresses in the fibers of cotton stems increase by 20.4 % (from 2.94 to 3.54 MPa). The average stresses in the components of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete at the time of destruction of the sample can be called the strength of the cellulose organic aggregate or the mortar part used. As follows from the data obtained (**Fig. 2**), the strength of the crushed fiber of cotton stems is most fully manifested in the first section, so, with the initial strength of the mortar part of 30 and 55 MPa, the strength of the crushed fiber of cotton stems and slag-alkaline mortar components are almost equal. With an increase in the initial strength of the slag-alkali solution, the strength of the organic aggregate used increases. At the same time, in such cases, the reverse pattern was observed in Portland cement arbolite concrete. The results obtained (**Tables 9–11**) indicate that the compression of the fiber of cotton stems, which takes place in the considered slag-alkaline arbolite concrete, increases its strength. This makes it possible for such arbolite concrete to withstand a higher destructive load ($N_{experience}/N_{Calculation} > 1$).

Fig. 2. Model II of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete and average stresses in concretes 1, 2, 3 (according to **Table 4**) and their components: Δ – slag-alkaline arbolite concrete; \circ – slag-alkaline mortar part; \square – crushed fibers of cotton stems

Table 11

Calculation results for samples with cotton stems fibers taking into account the role of comprehensive compression

Composition number according to Tables 9, 10	$N_{experiences}$ T	$N_{calculations}$ T	$N_{experience}/N_{Calculation}$	σ_{arb} , MPa	σ_r , MPa
1	2.71	2.60	1.08	2.94	30.3
2	3.95	3.95	1.01	3.54	43.6
3	2.37	1.25	1.11	1.47	15.3
4	–	–	–	2.92	30.5
5	–	–	–	1.21	13.5

The characteristics of the mortar component and the organic aggregate made from crushed cotton stem fiber are more similar in slag-alkaline arbolite concretes than in Portland cement arbolite concretes. As a result of the tightly reinforced arbolite concrete's advantageous structure and decreased stress concentration in the solution and filler's contact zone, this situation.

We are currently considering a research of the methods used to create the slag-alkaline arbolite structure from crushed cotton stem fibers. It should be mentioned that the phenomenon and patterns seen at the interface «slag-alkaline binder solution – organic filler» had a significant role in the construction of the structure of slag-alkaline arbolite. Thus, physicochemical reactions occur at the «arbolite – slag-alkaline solution» contact after mixtures are mixed with an alkaline solution; the nature of these reactions is dictated by the adhesive bonds between the organic fillers and the slag-alkaline binder stone. Also, the porous nature of arbolite plays a significant role in the absorption of moisture by the material shortly after the mixture is prepared. This causes an increase in adhesive contacts between the slag-alkaline binder and the rough surfaces of cotton stems. A sort of «epitaxial» deposition of Na^+ ions on the surface of cotton stems that have dissolved in solution is possible because, as the binder stone hardens, a cation exchange occurs between the Na^+ of the alkaline component and the Ca^{2+} of the slag. This results in the formation of a caustic alkali. The interaction processes between the binder and the organic filler become more intense due to the increasing salt concentration in the contact zones of the slag-alkaline binder with porous aggregates. Mixed adhesive-cohesive contacts are created on the contact as a result of chemisorption. When the hydration process deepens and the volume of the gel-like phase increases, the hydration products of the slag-alkaline binder, which share ions with an organic filler substrate, will make a more thick and long-lasting contact with it. It is important to note that the nature of the first period curve changes is compatible with the experimental data on similar systems obtained by the resonance of forced oscillations of the hardening system. When compositions are studied using the acoustic interferometer method for the first time minutes after closure, the values alter, indicating a change in the compositions' structural properties during the creation of the coagulation structure (stage I). As is common knowledge, uncured arbolite concrete exhibits a significant attenuation of high-frequency ultrasonic waves in comparison to arbolite that has already hardened. While employing the pulsed ultrasound approach, the appearance and modification of values show that strong contact bridges between neoplasms are generated. As a result, at later phases of hardening, a matrix of upcoming high-strength structures is created. The type of the alteration suggests that the processes of neoplasm aggregation and dispersion, which are typical of the time of formation of the coagulation structure, are weakening at this point (stage II). Further hardening processes strengthen (the start of stage III), compaction occurs, and there is a sharp rise in the number of crystalline neoplasms. The strength of the slag-alkaline binding stone arbolite, which increases from a daily 7.8 MPa at ages 3 and 7 days to 19 and 28 MPa, respectively, confirms this as well. Regardless of the composition of the latter, the system «slag-alkaline binder-organic filler» is greatly reinforced during the creation of the spatial framework of the crystalline structure of the binder in the composition of arbolite, as shown by the rise in strength.

We also talk about how the structure of slag-alkaline arbolite develops during the hardening process and in light of data from measurements of deformation in the filler, contact zone, and mortar component. It is well known that the type of alkaline component and slag has an impact on how quickly the structure develops during the early phase of the hardening material's maximal hardening. Analysis of the features of the structure formation of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete mixtures based on the alkaline components Na_2CO_3 (sodium corbanate) and Na_2SiO_3 (sodium silicate or metasilicate), Na_2SO_3 (sodium sulfite), Na_2SO_4 (Sodium sulfate), (**Tables 9, 10** compositions 1, 2 and 3) showed that the formation of the coagulation and crystallization structure of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete on Na_2SiO_3 (Sodium silicate or metasilicate) occurs more intensively than on Na_2CO_3 (sodium corbanate). The earliest phases of the structure-formation process of the slag-alkaline arbolite concrete mixture are intensified due to an increase in the liquid phase's reactivity when the alkaline component Na_2SiO_3 (sodium silicate or metasilicate) is used. The increased strength of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete made from blast furnace and electrothermophosphoric slag serves as proof of this. The strength is therefore 1.68 and 1.60 MPa by the daily age, or 32 and 30 % of the strength from the 28-day age, respectively. The strength reaches 77 and 71 % (3.7 and 3.9 MPa) from the age of 28 days, respectively, at the age of 7 days. Slag-alkali binders and concretes based on electrothermophosphoric slag and non-silicate salts of alkali metals are noted for having poor strength under conditions of natural hardening and a slower development of structure formation processes. Very basic additives, such as Portland cement clinker, are added to the mix of binders to

produce ones with qualities that are similar to one another. It can be assumed that the processes that occur between the cotton stem fibers and the slag-alkaline binder during the hardening of arbolite, in creating a dense, durable contact layer between them, increasing the overall strength and solidity of concrete, are reduced to improving the conditions for the joint work of individual structural components of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete under the action of destructive forces. Comparing the results of experiments conducted on samples made using Portland cement and samples made using a slag-alkali binder revealed (compositions 3 and 5 of **Tables 9, 10**) that even when cotton stems and mortar have the same strength, adding crushed fiber produces quite different outcomes. At the same time, a slag-alkaline solution's modulus of elasticity is 40 % more than a Portland cement solution's modulus of elasticity for cotton stems. This is as a result of the increased adhesive force between the binder stone and the crushed cotton stems in slag-alkaline arbolite concrete. The results of investigations on the strength of cotton stalk fiber in the slag-alkali test support the formation of a dense shell in the contact zone, which results in the strengthening of the arbolite concrete structure. In a slag-alkali test using a sodium sulfate mixture and Na_2SiO_3 (sodium silicate or metasilicate) (compositions of binding compositions 1 and 2 according to **Tables 9, 10**) in a Portland cement test, cotton stalks of the same size that had been ground on both sides of the fiber were saturated for one hour at $P/W=0.8$ and 1.0 and $V/C=0.8$. After heat and moisture treatment, the cotton stem fiber's strength test revealed that it increased by 6 % in the Portland cement test, 30 % in the slag-alkali test on a sodium sulfate mixture, and 16 % in the Na_2SiO_3 (sodium silicate or metasilicate) test. The cotton stem fiber's initial average strength was 2.0 MPa (3.1 MPa). This is as a result of cotton stem fiber strength being significantly increased in slag-alkaline arbolite concrete. The way the samples were destroyed is another indication of the above legitimacy. In samples with fiber cotton stems based on a slag-alkaline binder, deterioration solely affects the solution component and organic filler, regardless of composition. The cotton stem fiber's strength rose by 6 % in the Portland cement test, 30 % in the slag-alkali test on a sodium sulfate combination, and 16 % in the Na_2SiO_3 (sodium silicate or metasilicate) test following heat and moisture treatment. The initial average strength of the cotton stem fiber was 2.0 MPa (3.1 MPa). This is because slag-alkaline arbolite concrete considerably increases the strength of cotton stem fiber. Another sign of the validity of the information above is how the samples were destroyed. Regardless of composition, only the solution component and organic filler deteriorate in samples with fiber cotton stems made from a slag-alkaline binder. The latter enhances the interaction of the various slag-alkaline arbolite concrete structural elements. There is a decrease in the stress concentration in the contact zone, which is known to be the most dangerous area in arbolite concrete, as a result of the ultimate deformative properties of the solution and the organic aggregate, which differ greatly from one another, becoming more similar in their indicators. This explains how high-strength arbolite concrete is produced on porous cellulose organic aggregates with low strength. To demonstrate, the destructive load of an arbolite concrete sample is calculated without accounting for the filler's compression. The calculation's outcomes were contrasted with the destructive load measured experimentally on a sample made of cotton stem fibers, accounting for the importance of the compression's totality (**Fig. 2, Table 11**). The latter improves how the various slag-alkaline arbolite concrete structural components interact with one another. The ultimate deformative characteristics of the solution and the organic aggregate, which differ substantially from one another, become more comparable in their indicators, resulting in a decrease in the stress concentration at the contact zone, which is recognized to be the most dangerous place in arbolite concrete. This describes how high-strength cellulose organic aggregates are created on porous aggregates with low strength. To illustrate, the destructive load of a sample of arbolite concrete is computed without taking the compression of the filler into consideration. The results of the computation were compared with the destructive load that was determined experimentally on a sample made of cotton stem fibers, explaining the significance of the entire amount of compression (**Fig. 2, Table 11**).

Our study refers to a group of lightweight concrete conglomerates with a composite, fibrous structure, whose main components include particles of organic aggregate of plant origin and various mineral binders. Due to the low strength and low average density, the wall materials under development can be used in the form of heat insulation and structural materials only in low-rise civil engineering.

To develop research and obtain effective lightweight concrete can be based on the use of high-strength binders to maximize the strength of the mortar part of the concrete with the full realization of the properties of organic aggregate, and thereby provide optimal conditions for the formation of arbolite structure, which has increased compressive strength and low density.

As shown by our research, unlike other concretes, the destruction of arbolite samples occurs in stages, first the destruction occurs in the mortar component (first phase) and then there is a destruction of the organic aggregate (second phase). For this reason, our material can be used for buildings in earthquake-prone regions.

4. Conclusions

A deep, long-lasting contact layer forms during the structure-building process between a slag-alkaline binder and a cellulose organic filler made of crushed cotton fiber stems, which helps create high-strength arbolite concrete from porous, low-strength organic fillers.

Two portions make up the strength of slag-alkaline arbolite concrete when compared to the original strength of the solution, and they represent the first and second phases of the material's operation. No of the composition, only the solution component and organic filler are destroyed in samples with fiber cotton stems based on a slag-alkaline binder. According to the grain fraction or the size of the organic filler fiber, the studies undertaken allow for the planning of the fabrication of efficient wall bearing and enclosing structures made of arbolite composites containing sulfur.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding this research, including financial, personal, authorship or other nature that could affect the research and its results presented in this article.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

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